

How can the CAP foster crop diversification? A bio-economic farm-modelling approach

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Abstract

Greater diversity in crop rotations is associated with multiple environmental benefits and is therefore included in several measures of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Understanding the economic implications of policies that promote crop diversification is crucial for their design and for aligning economic and environmental objectives, particularly in light of the upcoming post-2027 CAP reform. We apply a bio-economic farm model to typical farms in the German federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia to assess the costs of different crop-rotation diversification scenarios under the CAP's Conditionality requirements. Our results reveal substantial heterogeneity in costs across farm types, ranging, for example, from €56.63 to €152.31 per hectare for the inclusion of legumes in the crop rotation. For the dairy farm considered, the most ambitious diversification scenario even makes exiting the direct payment scheme economically advantageous. Sensitivity analyses show that the decision to exit the direct payment scheme is strongly influenced by the level of premiums and output prices. Overall, our findings call into question uniform compensation mechanisms for crop diversification, particularly in the context of agri-environmental schemes. They provide insights that can support policymakers in designing more targeted and economically viable measures under the CAP post-2027.

1 Introduction

Greater diversity in crop rotations is associated with multiple environmental benefits, including lower pesticide use (Guinet et al., 2023) and enhanced biodiversity (Beillouin et al., 2021). It can also improve yield performance (Beillouin et al., 2019) and stabilize national food production by reducing output variability (Renard and Tilman, 2019). Through these effects, crop rotations contribute to both food security and the resilience of farming systems. Recognizing these benefits, policymakers promote more diverse rotations using a range of policy instruments. Under the current EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), crop diversification is included in the obligations associated with receiving direct payments, such as Greening or Conditionality. It is also a common voluntary measure under agri-environmental schemes. With the post-2027 CAP approaching rapidly, there is an increasing need for ex ante research on policy measures that promote crop diversification and inform evidence-based policy decisions. In particular, understanding the economic consequences for farmers is crucial to reconcile environmental objectives with farm viability and to strengthen support for future CAP reforms. Previous policy decisions were partly questioned and even rescinded due to farmers' protests, which were closely linked to their economic impact. This paper, therefore, addresses the question of how costly different policy options to foster crop diversity are for farmers.

Analyzing the economic consequences of policies before they can be observed empirically is inherently challenging. This is particularly true for CAP measures, which apply to a highly diverse farming sector and may therefore have widely varying impacts. Bio-economic farm models are well-suited to address these challenges because they simulate individual farms, allowing the heterogeneity of impacts to be captured and enabling the assessment of future policy options that have not yet been implemented. Furthermore, farm models can account for the agronomic and economic interdependencies on farms, such as sunk costs for machinery or livestock feed requirements. This approach provides more realistic cost estimates than static calculation methods.

Past CAP measures aimed at promoting crop diversity have been assessed using econometric approaches in various EU member states (e.g., Diop and Védrine, 2025). In addition, more general analyses of the costs of diversification are available (e.g., Ang et al., 2018). However, assessments of policy options for the future development of the current Conditionality requirements on crop diversity remain scarce. Kuhn et al. (under review) provide a static estimation of opportunity costs for two crop diversity scenarios, assessing gross margin changes at the field level. Apart from this, no analysis exists that evaluates policy options for crop diversification using the current CAP as a baseline.

Hence, we contribute an ex-ante analysis of policy options to advance current crop diversity measures. To do so, we apply the bio-economic farm model FarmDyn (Britz et al., 2021) to typical farms of the German federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, using detailed and current information on observed crop sequences (Kuhn et al., under review). The state is characterized by a very heterogeneous and partly intensive farming structure, showing likely diverse impacts of the uniform CAP policies.

The manuscript is organized as follows. In the methodology section, we describe the case study region and the data, the FarmDyn model with a focus on the representation of crop sequences, and the scenarios. We present the results before discussing the methodology, results, and policy implications. Finally, we conclude from a policy and research perspective.

2 Methodology

2.1 Case study region and farm data

The federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) is in western Germany, borders the Netherlands and Belgium, and is characterized by an intensive, diverse agricultural sector. Agricultural land consists of both grassland and arable areas, with arable farming accounting for the larger share of arable land. Major crops typically include cereals, maize, oilseeds, and sugar beet. Agricultural production varies considerably across regions due to differences in soil quality, topography, and historical development. The southern Rhineland is known for fertile soils and specialized arable farming. In the northern Rhineland, mixed systems combining arable forage production with dairy farming are standard. The low mountain regions in the south are dominated by permanent grassland and grassland-based dairy production, with only limited arable agriculture. The Münster region features livestock-intensive systems, particularly pig and cattle fattening, often on lighter soils with lower yield potential. In East Westphalia, livestock production is combined with comparatively intensive arable farming on more productive soils. Vegetable production concentrates near urban centers, especially in the Rhineland. Compared to many other European regions, NRW also has a high density of biogas plants, particularly in the state's northern parts.

Crop diversity in North Rhine-Westphalia is highly heterogeneous, as detailed by Kuhn et al. (under review). The northern part of the state, including the intensive livestock-producing region of Münsterland, exhibits low crop rotation diversity, with only a few crops, dominated by winter cereals and maize. In contrast, the Rhineland shows high diversity, with rotations that combine cereals and leaf crops and include a broader range of species. However, areas characterized by intensive arable fodder and dairy production tend to have less diverse crop rotations. The low mountain ranges in the southern part of the state, where permanent grassland and dairy farming predominate, display medium levels of crop rotation diversity.

Table 1: Typical farms for the case study analysis

	Dairy farm	Arable RR	Arable MS
Crop rotation	MA-MA-WB-MA-MA-WB-MA	WW-WW-SB-WW-WW-SB-WW	WW-WG-MA-WW-WG-MA-WW
Arable land (ha)	74.04	123.02	62.40
Permanent grassland (ha)	54.42	3.00	1.96
Dairy cows (LU)	193	-	-

We selected three typical farms from the typology developed by Kuhn & Schäfer (2018), summarized in Table 1. The selected dairy farm represents 10.16% of the dairy cows, 1.90% of farm land, and 0.57% of total farms. 44% of the farms in this type are located in soil climate region 142, which covers the intensive dairy farming in the Lower Rhine region. The rotations are characterized by a high share of silage maize, combined with winter cereals.

The arable farm Arable RR represents 1.21% of farmland and 0.38% of farms. 34.12% of farms are located in soil-climate region 141, which covers the fertile soils of the Rhineland. The rotations of this type are dominated by winter cereals, sugar beet, and partly maize. Finally, the arable farm Arable MS represents 2.90% of farmland and 1.78% of farms in the region. They are, amongst others, strongly found in the soil climate regions 142 and 148, covering the Münsterland region. The rotation of this farm type is dominated by maize and winter cereals.

The crop-share information for the typology from Kuhn & Schäfer (2018) is combined with the crop-sequence typology from Kuhn et al. (under review). The typology uses an approach developed by Stein & Steinmann (2018) that groups seven-year crop sequences into different levels of functional and structural diversity, using plot-level data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS). The data provided from Kuhn et al. (under review) contains detailed information on the regional and quantitative distribution of the different crop sequence types that allows for aligning the typical farms and typical rotations, as shown in Table 1.

2.2 FarmDyn model

FarmDyn is a mixed-integer linear programming model that captures farm-level decision-making. It assumes a fully informed and rational decision maker who seeks to maximize farm profit through optimal management choices, including crop selection, fertilization, manure management, herd composition, and feeding strategies (Figure 1). The model provides a detailed representation of relevant farming activities by integrating biophysical and economic processes across different production systems. The factor endowment of the farm, such as land and labour, and policies, are the core restrictions of the model. It is parameterized using planning data, official statistics, and expert knowledge. The FarmDyn model has been described in detail in the literature (e.g., Kokemohr et al., 2026; Kuhn et al., 2020). In this study, we apply FarmDyn in a comparative-static framework. The current Conditionality serves as a baseline, which we compare to the scenarios described in the following paragraph.

Figure 1: Overview of the FarmDyn model (own figure based on Lengers & Britz (2012))

For this study, the crop rotation module of FarmDyn is revised and transferred from a three to a seven year sequence, to align with the data from Kuhn et al. (under review). Every typical farm is calibrated to the observed crop rotation, using the approach from Britz (2021).

Alternative rotations with a different diversity level are included as management options to allow adaptation to the different scenarios.

2.3 Policy scenarios and sensitivity analysis

Our analysis focuses on the Conditionality that farmers need to fulfill to receive direct payments under the CAP. The Conditionality has one measure to foster crop diversity, also registered as measure 7 under the Good agricultural and environmental conditions. Currently, reflected in the baseline scenario, farms have to change crops at the latest in the third year (Table 2). On $\frac{1}{3}$ of their land, they have to change annually or grow a catch crop. This is a relaxed version of the original Conditionality due to the geopolitical situation and farmers' protests in the past. The requirements before, reflected by scenario 1, obliged farmers to change crops annually on $\frac{1}{3}$ of their land and to change crops annually or to grow catch crops annually on the second $\frac{1}{3}$ of their land. Farmers must change crops on all land at the latest in the third year. In addition, we assess two more far-reaching versions of the Conditionality requirements. In Scenario 2, farmers must change crops on every plot on an annual basis. In Scenario 3, farmers must rotate crop groups annually and cultivate legumes at least once every seven years on each plot.

Table 2: Baseline and policy scenarios

Baseline	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Current conditionality	Old conditionality	Change every year	Change every year + legumes at least every 7 years
Change crop in the third year, on $\frac{1}{3}$, change annually or grow a catch crop	German farmers were obliged a) to change crops annually on $\frac{1}{3}$ of their land and b) to change crops annually or to grow catch crops annually on the second $\frac{1}{3}$ of their land. Farmers must change crops on all land at the latest in the third year	Change the crop every year on all plots.	Change the crop every year on all plots and legume every seven years.

The economic implication of the different scenarios are influenced by variables exogenous to the FarmDyn model and linked to high uncertainty. To capture their effect on the results, we provide a sensitivity analysis on the impact of output prices and amount of direct payments. Thereby, we focus on the aspect under which circumstances farmers exit the direct payment scheme. To do so, we provide a Monte-Carlo analysis where every observation represents a model run with specifically drawn combinations of direct payments (25 to 250 Euro ha⁻¹) and output prices (factor 0.75 to 1.25).

3 Results

Our results reveal that the costs to fulfill the requirements of the Conditionality on crop diversity are heterogeneous (Figure 2). The typical farm Arable MS does not face any additional costs in scenario 1, the past Conditionality requirements, and in scenario 2, the annual change of crops. The crop sequences of this farm, being maize - winter wheat - winter barley, features already an annual change of crops. However, in scenario 4, which requires farms to introduce legumes once in seven years, Arable MS faces costs of 56.63 Euro ha⁻¹, mainly caused by the lower sales revenues from legumes compared to alternatives.

Figure 2: Costs of the assessed typical farms in the scenarios

In contrast, the farm Arable RR, with a high share of winter wheat in its rotation, faces costs in all scenarios. In scenario 1, costs of 36.33 Euro ha⁻¹ occur, and in scenario 2, costs of 74.27 Euro ha⁻¹. When introducing legumes additionally, the costs are 121.90 Euro ha⁻¹ and, hence, more than double that of the farm Arable MS in the same state. Again, costs are largely driven

by the lower sales revenues when introducing winter barley and legumes as alternatives to winter wheat in the rotation. However, quitting the direct payment scheme is financially worse for this farm in all scenarios.

Finally, the farm Dairy faces the highest costs. In scenario 1, costs of 37.64 Euro ha⁻¹ occur, and in scenario 2, costs of 83.31 Euro ha⁻¹ occur. When introducing legumes, the farm exits the direct payment scheme, causing a loss of 152.31 Euro ha⁻¹. Compared to the specialized arable farms, the main cost drivers are the reduction of maize in the crop sequence and the need to replace it partly with bought fodder. Hence, compared to the arable farms, not the sales revenues but the higher costs cause the costs for compliance with the policy.

Figure 3: Changes in different cost components of the typical dairy farm

Hence, the policy impacts various economic variables in the FarmDyn model and, consequently, on farms. In Figure 3, we exemplarily show for the dairy farm the detailed policy impact for two scenarios. In the baseline, the sales revenues and direct payments offset the machinery costs, input costs like fertilizer, and costs for bought feeds. In scenario 2 with annual change of crops, the costs for bought feeds increase by around 30 Euro ha⁻¹ and sales revenues decrease by around 140 Euro ha⁻¹. In scenario 3, when annual crop change and legumes become compulsory, the farm exits the direct payment scheme, allowing it to even increase the maize share compared to the baseline and lower the need to buy external fodder.

This causes, compared to baseline, a slight increase in sales revenues and a slight decrease in costs for bought feeds, leading to a total cost of 152.31 Euro ha⁻¹ when the loss of the direct payments is considered. The machinery costs and input costs for land use stay relatively constant as they are comparable for the crops that change between the scenarios.

Figure 4: Sensitivity analysis on direct payment and output prices for a typical farm Arab R

Finally, the results and the exit of the direct payment scheme from an economic point of view are strongly dependent on the output price level and the amount of direct payments, as shown in Figure 4. When varying the direct payment between 25 and 250 Euro ha⁻¹ and the output prices between the factor 0.75 and 1.25, we simulate a possible exit of the direct payment scheme. However, when analyzing the past Conditionality, farms are economically better off exiting the direct payment scheme in cases where direct payments are extremely low (under 75 Euro ha⁻¹), and output prices are relatively high (factor above 0.95). In scenario 2, where crops need to change annually, farms start to exit the direct payment scheme at a level of around 125 Euro ha⁻¹ when output prices are very high. Also, at an output price level as assumed in the scenario analysis (factor 1), direct payment below 90 Euro ha⁻¹ causes farms to exit the direct payments in the modelling analysis.

4 Discussion

Our results show that the costs to comply with stricter requirements on crop diversity are heterogeneous. The analyzed typical dairy farm shows the highest costs, causing even the

exit of direct payments when legume cultivation becomes compulsory. Exit of direct payments strongly depends on the amount of payment and output prices. Our results are in line with previous research. Kuhn et al. (under review) also find heterogeneous costs when estimating compliance costs for higher diversity with a static gross margin approach at the field level. They identify the highest costs for vegetable production, which is currently not covered by FarmDyn. Similar to the typical farm Arable MS, they identify that only 8.53% of the land is affected by the current Conditionality, although not covering all its dimensions due to data limitations. Reiter and Röder (2023) identify sequences with maize as having the highest costs to fulfill the Conditionality, which is in line with our findings. In contrast, Ang et al. (2018) also find negative costs when farms diversify, which is not possible when calibrating FarmDyn to an observed less-diverse sequence.

Using a bio-economic farm model, such as FarmDyn, offers several advantages compared to static, field-level approaches, such as that proposed by Kuhn et al. (under review). It captures farm-level interlinkages that influence the actual costs faced by farmers, for example, the need to produce or purchase fodder for livestock. Furthermore, it facilitates comprehensive scenario and sensitivity analyses at relatively low additional cost. However, several limitations of the approach should be acknowledged. First, the model assumes a fully informed and perfectly rational decision-maker. This implies that farmers cannot further improve their economic returns within the simulated scenarios. In reality, however, farmers do not always choose optimal activities or management strategies and may adjust more flexibly to policy-induced changes, potentially improving their returns. Second, FarmDyn assumes standard profit-maximizing behavior and does not account for behavioral heterogeneity, such as differences in risk attitudes. Particularly with regard to direct payments, which are largely independent of market and production risks, risk-averse farmers may respond differently than predicted by the model. Third, transaction costs associated with applying for direct payments are not considered, as general management costs are assumed to be constant in FarmDyn. This assumption may underestimate the attractiveness of exiting the direct payment scheme if stricter requirements are introduced. Fourth, FarmDyn is a supply-side model with exogenous

prices. If policy measures induce structural crop changes at a larger scale—such as increased legume cultivation—price feedback effects may occur, which cannot be captured within the current modeling framework. Finally, independent of the modeling approach, the study is limited by the relatively small farm sample analyzed. The results should therefore be interpreted as exploratory rather than fully representative.

From a policy perspective, our results show the heterogeneity in costs associated with diversification and the farm's exit from the direct payment scheme, especially when stricter measures, lower payments, and higher output prices jointly take effect. Our results can serve policymakers as a benchmark for which measures go with which payments, and to estimate the number of farms potentially exiting the direct payment scheme. However, we only consider part of the Conditionality in our scenarios. When the other Conditionality measures also change, this will affect the costs farms face in complying. The discussion on the CAP post-2027 is ongoing, and the Conditionality in its current form will likely not be continued. Our results are, however, also relevant for other policy frameworks when addressing crop diversity. Estimating the costs for heterogeneous farms to comply with a policy is relevant not only for the analysis of the Conditionality but also for optional agri-environmental measures. This allows policymakers to better understand how to design measures to achieve the targeted adoption level and participation of specific farm types.

5 Conclusion

We assess the compliance costs for farms under different scenarios of crop-rotation diversification within the CAP's Conditionality. Our results show that costs are very heterogeneous between farm types, for instance, ranging from 56.63 to 152.31 Euro ha⁻¹ for the inclusion of legumes in the crop rotation. The assessed dairy farm is even better off economically when exiting the direct payment scheme in the most far-reaching diversification scenario. Sensitive analysis reveals that exiting the direct payment scheme is strongly influenced by the amount of premium paid and the output price level.

From a policy perspective, we conclude the following. First, the heterogeneous costs of diversification question the uniform compensation mechanisms reflected in the CAP, especially for optional agri-environmental measures. Policy makers need to consider staggered payments dependent on farm characteristics and location. However, such differentiation must always be evaluated in light of transaction costs and the political economy. Second, our results can provide insights into the level of payments that are needed to prevent farms from exiting the direct payment scheme under different diversification policies.

We use a bio-economic farm model for our assessment, especially suited as it allows us to capture farm heterogeneity and interlinkages between different farm branches. Its linkage to large-scale equilibrium models would allow for including market feedback on the assessed policies. Furthermore, future research can use the developed modelling approach on a larger farm sample, covering regions beyond the study area, and can also address agri-environmental schemes.

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AI use

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly and ChatGPT to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. All content generated with the help of the tools was carefully reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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